

An Evaluation of Facilities Management Practice of Event Centres in Auchi, Edo State

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ABSTRACT

Facilities management practice has been known to enhance the peculiarity of a space, making spaces adaptable to multipurpose use, without altering any functional requirements. The design features and techniques that allow for changing situations in the use and operation of spaces are the focus of this paper. Components such as walls, floors and roofs are the design features that affect space in any building. Event centers being hubs for cultural and social activities, attract an unpredictable population, hence the need for a perfect venue for event centres which are fast becoming stable and developing features of any city. The study assessed the evaluation of facilities management practice of event centres, examining their adaptation to the inadequacy of event spaces in some selected event centres in Auchi. Observation schedules were used as instruments to obtain data, the data collected was then analyzed. It was observed from the study that all event centres had adaptability as their flexible design approach and this is as a result of the use of large open spaces, however, some of these event centres fail to have good/suitable design features. Planned and preventive maintenance should be taken regularly in order to enhance the effectiveness of the facilities management and to satisfy both the owner and customers of the organization. It was recommended that design features such as moveable walls, retractable roofs, and sitting should be used in event centre designs to achieve an effective event centre design.

Key words: Facilities management, Event centres, Space, Adaptability, Cultural and social activities, Auchi

1. INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, facility management became necessary as there arose a need to improve the state of decaying infrastructural facilities within the country. These efforts were revealed in the introduction of the Petroleum Trust Fund which was commonly known as PTF, which had its major objective aimed at improving the condition of National facilities which ranges from roads, hospital facilities, and educational facilities. In the same vein, private organizations like banks and oil-producing firms in line with high competition in industries and increased organizational complexity have implemented facility management in a bid to concentrate on the core business of their organizations; Non-core businesses are outsourced to specialist organizations possessing expertise in various aspects of facility management [1]. In line with this quest for efficiency and an improved environment, organizations demand the services of facility managers for the management of their facilities. As a result of this, facility management has become an interesting area in Nigeria. The increased national interest in facility management by different professionals have resulted in deep-seated misconception amongst professionals and the elite over the distinction between the practice areas of facility management and property management. Whereas property management falls within the core competency of the Estate Surveyors and Valuers, facility management is delivered by the integration of associated support services [2].

An organization is composed of people, facilities, and systems put in place to achieve specific objectives; one of which is to render service(s) in pursuit of money or in fulfilling social obligations. The people, the facilities, and the interplay of the systems in order to achieve a set goal. The facilities are composed of buildings, infrastructure, and support services. The system is the inter-link or a web that binds people and facilities together and turns them into a productive system. As a productive system, it is subject to wear and tear apart from the fact that both facilities and the people respond to the dictates of the life cycle. Smith [3], averred that facilities are another major cost centre and in most cases, the second-largest expenditure category regardless of whether space is owned or leased, ranking next to human resources.

Facilities are not necessarily confined to buildings but preferably considered as infrastructure that supports people, either individually or collectively, to realize their goals. Facility Management is about empowering people through the provision of infrastructure that adds value to the processes they support. Facility managers are charged with the responsibility of ensuring that infrastructure is available, operational, strategically aligned, safe, and sustainable. Above all, it encourages higher productivity through a continual search for ways to improve quality, reduce cost and minimize risk [4]. Thus, facilities have become dominant elements in organizational assets that cannot be dispensed with and its sustenance has gone beyond maintenance management or property management due to the need to meet the trinity of investment objectives which are to preserve capital, enhance its value, and earn net cash profit on the capital invested [5]. The trend now in Facilities Management is the practice of coordinating the physical workplace with the people and work of the organization, integrating the principles of business administration, architecture, behavioral, and engineering sciences.

Facilities Management is not completely new. From a British perspective, it is an offspring of maintenance management and property management whereas, from the American perspective, Facilities Management incorporates maintenance and property management and the specialties have expanded and broadened to become an instrument of change. According to Owen [6], Facilities Management became recognized as an identifiable management concept in the United States at the start of the eighties and has been practiced in the United Kingdom since 1983 with the main growth occurring in the nineties; all the functions, now incorporated under the Facilities Management umbrella existed prior to the recognition of Facilities Management. What Facilities Management has achieved, which is new, is the understanding that a coordinated and integrated approach to a range of business activities adds value to an organization's process.

The modern event centres authorities have diverse ownership varying from private individuals to organizations and agencies. Likewise, while some are stand-alone independent utilities, others are appendages of hospitality establishments. The observed identity differences would no doubt impinge upon their corporate goal and targets, especially in terms of whether they emphasize economic or social service to the community served [7]. Furthermore, given that the increasing popularity of event centres is associated with an evolving behavioural change in events celebration by the larger society suggests the likelihood for other equally relevant dimensions through which research may conceptualize and analyses issues on event centres and their services. In other words, to what extent are the differences respectively in the service-capacity profile and the relative competitiveness of the service-quality offered by the centres reflective of the differences in their rural-urban setting, or, of differences in the establishing (adoption) time of the studied event centres [4]. Therefore, this study is aimed at evaluating facility management practice of event centres in Auchi, Edo State.

1.1. Research Questions

This study put up a number of questions in respect of which credible answers were furnished in the course of the investigation. The said questions were:

1. Is facility management in Auchi formal or informal?
2. What methods of facility management are adopted?
3. What challenges are associated with facility management in the study?
4. What is the effectiveness of facility management in the study area?

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Research Design

After examining the various research designs, taking cognizance of the purpose and nature of this study it was concluded that the field survey design was the most appropriate. The field survey method involves the systematic gathering of data directly from the respondents through the use of questionnaires or oral interviews or a combination of the two, for the purpose of understanding some aspects of the behavior of the population of the study. The field survey design is considered appropriate for this study because it is amenable to situations where facts or data must be collected from respondents scattered in different locations and data collected from a sample of the target population was used to predict certain characteristics of the population.

2.2. Sources of Data Collection

The study adopted primary and secondary sources of data. Primary data were being generated through the use of oral interviews and questionnaires designed specifically for the study. The questions in the questionnaire are based on the key variables highlighted in the research questions. Unstructured personal interview was used to probe for more information where necessary. The Facilities Managers, the customers, and staff in the event centres were interviewed. Secondary data were generated through published journals, the internet, textbooks sources, official publications, and official gazettes, to back up the primary sources. The population of the study was made up of some event centres in the Auchi metropolis with a total number of 20 known event centres.

2.3. Data collection

2.3.1. Personal interview

The self-administered questionnaire was complemented by personal interviews especially at the initial stage of the data gathering process. Here the researcher armed with the interview schedule meets the respondent, asks questions from the respondents, and completes the interview schedule himself. There is an opportunity here to go beyond what is contained in the interview schedule to ask questions for clarifications in order to enrich the response. Moreover, interviews allow explanation of issues in the questionnaire by the interviewer in areas where some respondents may not be fully knowledgeable. The intention here is to frame questions in the form of a questionnaire, but administer the questionnaires in the manner of conducting personal interviews. Thus, core and crucial respondents such as the staff of these major event centres and customers of the event centres were covered.

2.3.2. Physical survey of constructed facilities

There was the need to physically inspect the event centres to establish the support services available, the extent of their operation, and the level of their patronage including an assessment of customers' satisfaction. This was achieved with a structured survey schedule that aided the preparation of a survey report from which necessary primary data were generated.

2.3.3. Documentary

Some document was used as sources of data for the study, such as the feed-books, pamphlets, and published journals which as well helped the researcher to determine the direction to investigate and the extent to which the researcher goes about his finding.

2.3.4. Questionnaires

This is a data collection method in which the subjects respond to questionnaires or scales or other devices used to measure variables. These are excellent measured. In this study, primary data was collected through administered questionnaires. Well-structured questionnaires were used to collect data from respondents because of the need to provide information clearly. They were delivered randomly to each designed cluster.

2.4. Validity of instrument

The instrument of research which is the questionnaire is valid because the items were structured to obtain information that will provide answers for the research questions. It is instrument valid because it was aimed at meeting the objective of the researcher.

2.5. Data presentation

This study has used the simple technique of data presentation. This has been done mainly by the use of tables in showing collected data particularly as regards the response obtained in respect of the study questionnaire. Data that are not in numerate form have been adequately presented and described in clear language for proper comprehension.

2.6. Data analysis

The research instrument used by the researcher was a combination of questionnaires, personal interview and document observation. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents. Frequencies and percentages were used in the study. The simple percentage method of data analysis was used to analyze data that were collected from the respondents. The data were analyzed in accordance with the response sought in the questionnaire to answer the four (4) research questions. The formula for the computation is shown in equation (1):

$$\frac{\text{Number of Responses}}{\text{Total Number of Respondent}} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (1)$$

3. RESULTS

3.1. Presentation

This study set out to evaluate the facility management practice of event centres in Auchu, Edo State. This chapter presented and analyzed the data collected as well as discussed, the findings. The data collection instrument used for this study is a self-developed questionnaire. A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of questionnaire were administered immediately to various respondents and one hundred twenty (120) were successfully retrieved. The sociodemographic features of the respondents, such as position, sex, age, marital status, and educational qualification were analyzed to give information on the background information of the respondents.

From the result in Table 1, 53 respondents representing 44% were within the age range of 20 - 25 years, 30 respondents representing 25% were within the age range of 26 - 30 years, 22 respondents representing 18% were within the age range of 31-35 years while 15 respondents representing 13% were 36-40 years Also, Fig.1 shows that , 40 respondents representing 33% are male while 80 respondents residing representing 67% are female.

Table -1 Age distributions of workers

Rating	Frequency	Percentage (%)
20 – 25 years	53	44
26 – 30 years	30	25
31 – 35 years	22	18
36 – 40 years	15	13
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

Fig. 1 Sex of the respondents

3.2. Patronage of event centres

It could be seen that the customers that visit these event centre are regular customers who have been using the event centres often; as such most of them are not new in these event centres. From the table 2, only 40 percent have visited and used these event centres for only about 0 - 4 times, the rest have used the event centres for above 5 times. From table 4.6, we can see that the major reasons customers patronize these event centres are due to the levels of technology and high-quality facilities in the event centres.

Table -2 Respondents use of the event centres

No of Times	Frequency	Percentage (%)
0-4 times	48	40
5-10 times	36	30
11-15 times	30	25
16-20 times	6	5
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

Table -3 Reasons respondents patronize the event centres

Reason	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Location	55	46
Level of Technology	40	33
High Quality Facilities	15	13
Fast Service Delivery	10	8
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

Table -4 Availability of Facilities

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
En-Suite Bathrooms	15	13
Swimming Pool	5	4
Tennis Court	5	4
Stand by Generator	15	13
Electricity from Public Main	10	8
Close Circuit System (CCTV)	10	8
Good Reception Hall	40	33
Fire-Fighting Equipment	20	17
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

From the result in table 4, we could discover that all the facilities in these event centres are available; this means that all the event centres are in 100 percent conformity to Facility Management (FM) standards set by the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation. This also means that all the event centres have the basic requirements set for an event centre to meet in order to be a standard event centre.

3.3. Conditions of event centres

From table 5, it was discovered that the hotel workers in the event centres agreed that all the issues raised are shortcomings of Facilities Management Practices in the Hospitality Industry. So in conclusion, we can say that the shortcomings in these event centres are as follows: lack of proper maintenance, inadequate maintenance performance standard, proactive approach in infrastructure, inadequate of facilities benchmarking, lack of fire safety plan, lack of creating the renovation plan, lack of complete record keeping and the maintenance of building and its systems are often neglected during the design and planning stage in project construction.

Table -5 Opinions of the event centre staffs on the shortcomings of facilities management practices

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of Proper Maintenance	24	20
Inadequate Maintenance Performance Standard	10	8
Proactive Approach in Infrastructure	13	11
Inadequate of Facilities Benchmarking	5	4
Lack of Fire Safety Plan	18	15
Lack of Creating the Renovation Plan	15	13
Lack of Complete Record Keeping	10	8
The maintenance of building and its systems are often neglected during the design and planning stage in project construction.	25	21
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

The challenges that may hinder holistic adoption of facilities management could be summarized to be the concern of immediate return on investment generally among investing event centres in a community which may not be possible in their operation and thus hampering inflow of capital into the industry. The un-conducive business environment in Auchi environment with regards to poor infrastructure while others are poor business promotion and marketing of event organizations in the community. Interestingly, authors like Alexander [8] and Opaluwah [9] look at the positive side of facilities management without a thought for the possible hindrances to enable proactive steps to be taken as a guide against such hindrances. The identification of these challenges will definitely spur policymakers into action in order to ensure the full attainment of the objectives of facilities management. The challenges are: conservatism among the stakeholders, conservatism among the built environments professionals, lack of legislation to backup practice management, inadequate training of facilities managers, conflict of supremacy among line managers, ignorance of facilities management in the hospitality industry, and absence of relevant database management system (Table 6).

Table -6 Challenges of facilities management practices in the hospitality industry as suggested by these event centres staffs

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Conservatism among the Stakeholders	20	17
Conservatism among the Built Environments Professionals	25	21
Lack of Legislation to Backup Practice Management	10	8
Inadequate Training of Facilities Managers	10	8
Conflict of Supremacy among Line Managers	25	21
Ignorance of Facilities Management in Hospitality Industry	20	17

Source: Field study, 2021

From the table 7, it could be deduced that the event centre workers in Auchi practice as what are effective and efficient for Facilities Management in the Hospitality Industry. The practices are: controlling cost, ensuring proper maintenance, tracking inventory, upgrading to automated building technology, coordinated teams, handling building failures, maintaining aging equipment and facilities, and preventive maintenance approach. However, result in table 8 shows that the customers agreed with seven of the practices, which the workers said, are not efficient and effective for Facilities Management in the Hospitality Industry, the only one they agreed with is "Coordinated Teams". The findings are in line with the studies of Rogers and Anastasiadou [10], Smith [11], and Suleiman *et al* [2]. Therefore, the customers in Auchi are of the opinion that the practices are not efficient and effective for facilities management in the Hospitality Industry, they are: controlling cost, ensuring proper maintenance, tracking inventory, upgrading to automated building technology, coordinated teams, handling building failures, maintaining aging equipment and facilities and preventive maintenance approach. Table 9 has the opinions of the hotel staff on the effects of lack of facility management on efficient productivity in the hospitality industry. From the table, we can see that all the issues raised have their own frequency and percentage this implies that the respondents are saying that the five issues are the effects that lack of facility management

usually has on the productivity/output in the hospitality industry. The effects are loss of customers, low patronage, low productivity, business failure, and bad record in the hospitality industry.

Table -7 Opinions of event centre staffs on practices that is efficient and effective for facilities management in the hospitality industry

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Controlling Cost	16	13
Ensuring Proper Maintenance	20	17
Tracking Inventory	5	4
Upgrading to Automated Building Technology	20	17
Handling Building Failures	25	21
Maintaining Aging Equipment and Facilities	20	17
Managing Time	5	4
Implementing Low and no Cost Energy Efficiency Measures	4	3
Preventive Maintenance Approach	5	4
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

Table -8 Opinions of customers on practices that is efficient and effective for facilities management in the hospitality industry

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Controlling Cost	10	8
Ensuring Proper Maintenance	40	33
Tracking Inventory	8	7
Upgrading to Automated Building Technology	20	17
Handling Building Failures	10	8
Maintaining Aging Equipment and Facilities	20	17
Managing Time	6	5
Implementing Low and no Cost Energy Efficiency Measures	-	-
Preventive Maintenance Approach	6	5
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

Table -8 Opinions of event centres staff on the effects of lack of facility management on efficient productivity in the hospitality industry

Issues Raised	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Loss of Customers	30	25
Low Patronage	25	21
Low Productivity	40	33
Business Failure	5	4
Bad Record to the Hospitality Industry	20	17
Total	120	100

Source: Field study, 2021

4. DISCUSSION

This Chapter has been able to present the findings. Based on the findings, various policy implications were highlighted among which are the need for the Nigerian Tourist Board to be more proactive in terms of event centre quality supervision; stepping up of undergraduate education, and in-service training in facilities management. Facilities management practitioners need to impress on the National assembly for the passing of an Act to back the establishment and control of facilities management as a profession.

5. CONCLUSION

The study has clearly shown that event centres are facilities that attract different categories of persons together and should be flexible enough to accommodate the needs of different users. In Etsako West, the study shows that the event centres do not have flexible design features that create or modify space for change requirements. Most of these adaptable spaces made use of racked concrete platforms for change in level with fixed seats making the space unable to adapt to changing activities of the event space. Related kinds of literature studied were able to proffer solutions to the flexibility of design features.

6. RECOMMENDATION

In the design of event centres, designers need to recognize the fact that event spaces are multipurpose spaces, therefore it is important to use design features for flexibility such as moveable walls, retractable roofs and sitting should be used in event centre designs to achieve an effective flexible design. Event centres attract an unpredictable population so space flexibility should be considered at all times and adopting all the flexible design approaches so that as the users' needs change, the building also changes to meet their needs.

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